

Graphical Abstract

Progress variable optimization: Effects on the manifold topology and reduced-order modeling

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Highlights

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- Encoder-decoder stretches out key regions on the optimized manifold.
- Trainable scaling layer amplifies the contribution of species in the PV definition.
- Log-transforming the decoded quantities of interest improves the manifold topology.
- Only a few species contribute effectively to the optimized PV definition.
- The optimized parametrization enhances model accuracy compared to the heuristic ones.

Progress variable optimization: Effects on the manifold topology and reduced-order modeling

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Abstract

Reduced-order models (ROMs) replace computationally expensive simulations of high-dimensional systems with cheaper surrogates. ROMs can be used to design, optimize, and control energy systems of industrial and engineering relevance, including reacting flows, electrochemical processes, thermal systems, and multiphysics energy devices. In reacting flow simulation, a common way to build a ROM is to project the original high-dimensional state-space onto a low-dimensional manifold, typically defined by a set of heuristic parameters being linear combinations of the original state variables. Recently, an encoder-decoder has emerged as a promising neural network architecture to automatically define and optimize the manifold parameterization. However, the literature lacks in-depth understanding of how optimized parameterizations improve the accuracy of ROMs compared to heuristic parameterizations. In this paper, an encoder-decoder is used to identify the

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optimized parameterization of the thermo-chemical state-space of a hydrogen combustion system. This leads to an improved representation of key quantities of interest (QoIs) and hence a more accurate ROM simulation when contrasted with heuristic parameterizations. The novel introduction of a trainable scaling layer prior to the encoder and a log-transformation of the highly non-linear decoded QoIs is found to be beneficial to smooth the QoI gradients on the manifold and it facilitates regression of the QoIs during ROM simulation. Moreover, we show that sparsifying the parameter definition is possible with no major impact on the manifold topology. We show how improvements in manifold parameterization lead to improved numeric simulations of reacting systems.

Keywords: Progress variable, hydrogen combustion, reduced-order modeling, neural network, trainable scaling

1. Introduction

Reduced-order models (ROMs) have gained increased attention as a substitute for high-fidelity models to speed up numerical simulations (1; 2; 3; 4). For many engineering applications, ROMs offer the possibility to design, optimize, and control energy systems at a lower computational cost compared to full-order models (FOMs) that solve the full set of governing partial differential equations (PDEs). In simulating reacting flows, one way to build a ROM is to project the complete thermo-chemical state-space onto a lower-dimensional basis (5; 6; 7). Typical variables to define the low-dimensional manifold are the mixture fraction (f), which defines the local stoichiometry, and the progress variable (PV), which measures the reaction progress. The

latter is often defined heuristically based on expert knowledge (8).

In recent years, the encoder-decoder architecture has been developed to automate and optimize manifold parameterization for reduced-order modeling (9; 10; 11; 12; 13; 14). The encoder projects linearly the full state-space onto the low-dimensional manifold, corresponding to re-formulating the governing equations as the reduced-order equations (15). Next, given the manifold, the decoder regresses non-linearly quantities of interest (QoIs) provided at the decoder's output. The non-linear regression of the QoIs is important to accurately evolve the ROM over time and reconstruct the original state-space (16). In this unified framework, the optimization of the linear projection learned by the encoder is automatically driven by the reconstruction of QoIs at the decoder.

Various successful implementations of the encoder-decoder exist in the literature for reacting flows. Zdybał *et al.* (11) introduced the QoI-aware encoder-decoder to optimize the low-dimensional manifold, driven by reconstruction of projection-dependent and projection-independent QoIs from the manifold. In that work, the optimized parameterization was compared with principal component analysis (PCA) and the improvements were measured *a priori* using the mean squared error (MSE), the coefficient of determination (R^2) and the cost function for manifold quality quantification (17). Similarly, Perry *et al.* (9) co-optimized the manifold parameters and the subgrid-scale surrogate model for large eddy simulations. Employing an encoder-decoder architecture, two progress variables and the subgrid-scale variances of the progress variables were optimized next to the internal energy and density. Subsequently, the manifold was compared *a priori* with PCA and flamelet-

generated manifold, a physics-based surrogate model, in terms of QoI reconstruction accuracy. Armstrong and Sutherland (12) proposed a variant of the encoder-decoder by replacing the decoding neural network with a Partition of Unity Network (POUnet) which was shown to be more accurate (18). They optimized a PV next to f , and then two PVs, training the encoder-decoder with hydrogen flamelets, idealized 1D flame simulations. They assessed the *a posteriori* accuracy of the ROM simulations against 1D and 2D high-fidelity direct numerical simulations. Zdybał *et al.* (13) adapted the encoder-decoder to optimize the PV next to f for ammonia/hydrogen combustion and showed how the optimized PV improved the *a priori* manifold parameterization compared to heuristic parameterizations. In that work, they showed for one test trajectory in a 0D reactor how an optimized PV outperforms heuristic PVs. In related fields, *i.e.*, hypersonic flows and turbomachinery reactors, Scherding *et al.* (10) and Rubini and Rosic (14) showed respectively successful implementation of projection-based ROMs using an encoder-decoder. Both showed accurate predictions of the ROM with respect to the FOM. However, an in-depth discussion linking the *a priori* manifold parameterization improvements and the *a posteriori* results from the ROM simulation is still missing in the existing literature.

In this work, we provide the link between the *a priori* assessment of the parameterization quality and the *a posteriori* impact on the ROM simulation. We compare different heuristic *vs.* optimized f -PV manifold parameterizations, obtained by an encoder-decoder, for a hydrogen flame dataset. We perform the analysis on a hydrogen flame containing NO_x species making it a challenging case to model with a single PV due to the differences in

timescales between the hydrogen-related and nitrogen-related reactions (8). First, we assess *a priori* the manifold topology quality of both parameterizations using the mean squared error (MSE) and the cost function for manifold quality quantification (17) (Section 5). Subsequently, we perform a surrogate transport simulation evaluating *a posteriori* the different heuristic *vs.* the optimized PV (Section 6). Thereby, we show in this paper how stretching out *a priori* key manifold regions leads to a reduced ignition time delay and improved QoI predictions during *a posteriori* simulations.

2. Methods

2.1. Combustion modeling background

The combustion process is governed by the reacting, multi-component transport equations that include the conservation of the total mass of the mixture, the mass of each component (chemical species) of the mixture, momentum, and energy. The conservation of mass for each component gives rise to transport of reacting scalars and is especially of interest here. For each species included in the combustion system, a partial derivative equation (PDE) has to be solved as per

$$\frac{\partial(\rho Y_i)}{\partial t} = -\nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u} Y_i) + \nabla \cdot (\rho D_i \nabla Y_i) + \dot{\omega}_i, \quad (1)$$

with Y_i and $\dot{\omega}_i$ being the mass fraction and the reaction source term of species i respectively, ρ being the density, and D_i being the diffusion coefficient. The first term of the right-hand side corresponds to the convection term, the second term to the diffusion term and the third term to the reaction source term coming from the kinetic mechanism. The computational burden

of combustion simulations comes from this transport equation since it has to be solved for every species included in the system. This typically yields tens to hundreds of PDEs (19), tightly coupled through hundreds to thousands of chemical reactions (20).

Taking advantage of the fact that reactive scalars are correlated in state space (5; 6; 7), the number of equations to solve can be drastically reduced. A few manifold parameters can be defined as a linear combination of the species' mass fractions. One common manifold parameter is the progress variable (PV) defined as $Y_{\text{PV}} = \sum_{i=1}^n w_i \cdot Y_i$ with w_i being the weight assigned to species i . The specific set of weights gives rise to the specific PV definition. Summing appropriately weighted Eq. (1) for all species and using the linearity of differentiation gives the following transport equation for the PV:

$$\frac{\partial(\rho Y_{\text{PV}})}{\partial t} = -\nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u} Y_{\text{PV}}) + \nabla \cdot (\rho D \nabla Y_{\text{PV}}) + \dot{\omega}_{\text{PV}}, \quad (2)$$

with the PV source term being defined as $\dot{\omega}_{\text{PV}} = \sum_{i=1}^n w_i \cdot \dot{\omega}_i$ and assuming the same diffusion coefficient for every species.

Next to the PV, the mixture fraction, f , is another variable frequently used to characterize the combustion process. The variable describes the ratio between oxidizer and fuel indicating the local stoichiometry of the mixture. Its definition is fixed and combines the mass fractions of elements H and O such that the source term of f is equal to zero (21; 22), which means that f is a conserved scalar. Hence, the transport equation for the mixture fraction is

$$\frac{\partial(\rho f)}{\partial t} = -\nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u} f) + \nabla \cdot (\rho D \nabla f), \quad (3)$$

assuming the same diffusion coefficient for every species. As a result, instead of solving tens to hundreds of PDEs as per Eq. (1), only a few equations

(*e.g.*, Eq. (2) together with Eq. (3)) need to be solved for the variables that parameterize efficiently the thermo-chemical combustion state-space.

In a homogeneous, closed reactor (a 0D reactor, or autoignition), the chemical reactions are taking place uniformly inside the reactor volume. Hence, the effects of transport processes such as convection and diffusion are neglected. As a result, no spatial gradients of chemical composition and temperature are present. Therefore, the f -PV system is only resolved in time and not in space. The system simplifies to the ordinary differential equation (ODE)

$$\frac{dY_{\text{PV}}}{dt} = \frac{\dot{\omega}_{\text{PV}}}{\rho}, \quad (4)$$

with an initial and constant mixture fraction $f_0 \in [0, 1]$ and the PV being initialized as $Y_{\text{PV}}(t = 0) = 0$ in case the PV has been scaled between 0 and 1.

When performing a ROM simulation of this autoignition case, these equations are evolved over time, which requires a mapping from the f -PV manifold to the PV source term as a replacement of the kinetic mechanism. Moreover, a second mapping from the input f -PV to the original state space is required. Although in a closed reactor f stays constant for the simulation of one 0D trajectory, f is still a necessary parameter to model the mappings at stoichiometries unseen in the training dataset.

The challenge in building such ROMs lies in the definition of the PV, being case-specific, to regress accurately the PV source term and the original state-space. The PV should be defined such that the mapping is unique and the gradient of every QoI in the state-space is smooth (23). Experts

usually rely on their knowledge to define the PV, typically combining the main products and reactants (24). However, this choice is often non-optimal for building an accurate ROM (13).

2.2. *QoI-aware encoder-decoder to optimize the PV*

The encoder-decoder, depicted in Fig. 1, is a neural network composed of an encoder and a decoder (9; 10; 11; 12; 13; 14; 25) to optimize the PV definition. The encoder reduces the mass fractions, Y_i , to an optimized PV, Y_{PV} , and parametrizes the manifold with the optimized PV and f . The definition of f is fixed and is directly fed to the input of the decoder. The relationship between the species mass fractions and the PV is linear and this considerably eases the formulation of the ROM equations as described in Section 2.1. Given the manifold parametrized by f and PV (26; 27), the decoder reconstructs the important QoIs. As opposed to the encoder, the decoder is non-linear to maximize the regression accuracy of the QoIs (16).

A separate, trainable scaling layer pre-processes the mass fractions prior to encoding. This results in $\tilde{Y}_i = s_i \cdot Y_i$ with s_i being the trainable scaling applied to every species. To the authors' knowledge, it is the first time that the scaling of the input features is learned automatically by the neural network itself. The goal is to integrate data scaling with learning the projection within one optimization problem. The encoder computes a linear combination of the scaled mass fractions to define the progress variable as $Y_{\text{PV}} = \sum_{i=1}^{n=19} w_i \cdot \tilde{Y}_i = w_i \cdot s_i \cdot Y_i$ with w_i being the weights of the encoder. Note that both the scalings, s_i , as the weights, w_i , are optimized and learned during the training phase. It is worth pointing out that the scaling could also be absorbed by creating a single projection layer with its new total weights

$w'_i = s_i w_i$. In principle, the encoder’s weights should be able to converge to some optimal w'_i and result in the same PV definition, without the need of creating a separate scaling layer. We find that the separation of the scaling and projection operations in the encoder promotes finding improved PV definitions. We elaborate on this point in Section 4.1.

The mixture fraction, f , defined by Bilger *et al.* (21), is directly used as one of the parameters defining the manifold. Given the f -PV parameterization, the decoder reconstructs the QoIs consisting of the temperature, T , the important subset of mass fractions, selected by the user and transformed to the logarithmic scale, $\log(Y_{S_i})$, and the PV source term, defined as $\dot{\omega}_{\text{PV}} = \sum_{i=1}^{n=19} s_i \cdot w_i \cdot \dot{\omega}_i$, where $\dot{\omega}_i$ is the mass production rate of species i . It is worth noting that the definition of the PV source term changes during training as the scaling and encoder weights are updated. The selection of QoIs at the output and their logarithmic transformation, based on prior knowledge of the process (28), are important as their reconstruction directly drives the topology of the f -PV manifold during training, as will be shown in Section 4.2.

Fig. 1: QoI-aware encoder-decoder architecture with a trainable scaling layer as the first layer of the network. \tilde{Y}_i values are the scaled mass fractions, $\tilde{Y}_i = s_i \cdot Y_i$, and the PV is a linear combination of the scaled mass fractions, $Y_{PV} = \sum_i^{n=19} s_i \cdot w_i \cdot Y_i$. A fixed weight equal to unity is used for f as it is explicitly used in manifold parameterization. At the output layer, the decoder reconstructs the temperature, T , the user-selected mass fractions in the logarithmic scale, $\log(Y_{S_i})$, and the PV source term divided by density, $\dot{\omega}_{PV}/\rho$.

2.3. The PV source term and the full state-space neural network models for a posteriori simulations

To perform the ROM simulation for a 0D reactor, described in Section 2.1, we trained two fully-connected artificial neural networks (ANNs) on the autoignition dataset to model the mapping from the f -PV parameterization to the PV source term, $\dot{\omega}_{PV}/\rho$, and to the full thermo-chemical state-space, being respectively called the PV source term model and the full state-space model. The hyperparameter settings for both ANNs are provided in Table 1.

The hyperparameters are based on the ones found for the encoder-decoder and tuned empirically to balance accuracy and training time as further explained below, prioritized as follows: the learning rate, the number of epochs, the architecture and the batch size.

The prediction accuracy of the PV source term is important because any perturbation to $\dot{\omega}_{\text{PV}}/\rho$ effectively changes the ODE solved in Eq. (4). Hence, errors can accumulate when evolving the PV over time (13). Therefore, a few measures were taken during data preprocessing and training of the ANN to achieve this higher accuracy. First, the complete dataset was used as a single batch as higher accuracy compared to mini-batching was observed as a result of this choice. The ANN architecture and the number of epochs were also larger than for the training of the encoder-decoder, provided in Section 3.2. In addition, the input manifold was reshaped to a rectangular manifold meaning that every trajectory was rescaled to the same length (8), illustrated in Section S3.1 of the supplementary material. This aligns the manifold boundaries associated with vanishing PV source terms (initial conditions and steady states) and helps the neural network to regress the small PV source terms accurately. To accurately predict the large PV source terms as well as the small, the neural network was trained to predict the logarithm of the PV source term. Concerning the negative PV source values, we applied the absolute value on them for two reasons. First, a previous study has reported that same-sign source term values are beneficial in regression tasks (12). Second, these negative values occurred only near the chemical equilibrium steady states (corresponding to the manifold boundary) where the PV source term was oscillating between vanishing positive and negative values.

	Hyperparameter	PV source term model	Full state-space model
<i>Data handling</i>	Rectangular manifold	Yes	Yes
	Input scaling	-0.5 to 0.5	-0.5 to 0.5
	Output scaling	-1 to 1	-1 to 1
	Batch size	Complete dataset	1000
	Validation percentage	10%	10%
<i>Network architecture</i>	Neurons (hidden layers)	[10, 20, 20, 20]	[11, 21, 21]
	Activation function – hidden	$\tanh(\cdot)$	$\tanh(\cdot)$
	Activation function – output	$\tanh(\cdot)$	$\tanh(\cdot)$
<i>Initialization</i>	Distribution weight init.	$\mathcal{N}(0, 0.05^2)$	$\mathcal{N}(0, 0.05^2)$
	Random seed number	7	7
<i>Optimization</i>	Optimizer	Adam	Adam
	Learning rate (Lr.)	0.025-0.00025	0.01-0.0001
	Lr. scheduler	Cosine (first 100k epochs)	Cosine
	Epochs	300000	500

Table 1: Hyperparameters for the training of the PV source term and the full state-space models, fully-connected ANNs to perform *a posteriori* simulations.

Overall, less than 1% of the dataset was associated with negative PV source term values and we observed this trend for all optimized parameterizations obtained throughout the analysis.

In the full state-space model, the architecture is smaller compared to the PV source term model and mini-batching was used, reducing considerably the training time. These hyperparameter modifications are justified by the fact that we do not need to be as accurate as for the PV source term predictions. Notably, while the error accumulates after each prediction for the PV source term, the predictions from the full state-space model at each time-step do not affect the model’s evolution in time.

2.4. Metrics

2.4.1. A priori manifold quality assessment

To assess the quality of the f -PV manifold parameterizations *a priori*, two metrics were used, *i.e.*, the cost function for manifold quality quantification, \mathcal{L}_{avg} , and the mean squared error (MSE) for quantity of interest (QoI) reconstruction from the manifold parameters. The cost function (17) quantifies the quality of the manifold topology with respect to gradients and non-uniqueness in QoIs. Meanwhile, the MSE measures how accurately a regression model can reconstruct the QoIs given the manifold parameterization.

To obtain the cost function (17), the \hat{D} -curve (29) has to be computed first. The curve is constructed by measuring how the different QoIs vary at different spatial scales over the manifold. It typically exhibits a single dominant peak corresponding to the main feature size. Additionally, the curve can contain secondary peaks at smaller scales revealing undesired high QoI gradients or non-uniqueness on the manifold. Subsequently, the cost function (17) is obtained by integrating the penalized \hat{D} -curve for a specific QoI over all spatial scales, summarizing the curve with one scalar value. This yields a single, comparable value that simplifies the assessment of different parameterizations. An individual cost, \mathcal{L}_j , is computed for every j th QoI from the set $\mathcal{Q}_{\text{a priori}} = \{T, Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}_2}, Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}, Y_{\text{H}_2}, Y_{\text{HO}_2}, Y_{\text{N}_2\text{O}}, Y_{\text{NO}_2}, Y_{\text{NO}}, Y_{\text{O}_2}, Y_{\text{OH}}, \dot{\omega}_{\text{PV}}/\rho\}$ and the average over all the QoIs is taken to have a single metric, $\mathcal{L}_{\text{avg}} = 1/m \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^m \mathcal{L}_j^2}$, where m is the number of QoIs. For the cost function, the vertical shift and the power are set to 1 and 4 respectively and 100 logarithmically-spaced bandwidth values (which determine the spatial

scales on the manifold) are used from 10^{-6} to 10^2 . To compute this metric, the PCAfold library was used (30; 31).

To assess how well the QoIs can be reconstructed from the f -PV manifold parameterization, which is relevant for a ROM simulation, a fully-connected ANN, similar to the full state-space model with f and PV as inputs and the QoIs as targets, is trained on a training subset of the dataset and assessed with MSE on the remaining, validation part of the dataset. The ANN hyper-parameters correspond to the exact same ones used for the full state-space model provided in Table 1 with the only difference that the PV source term is added as an additional QoI output of the ANN. The MSE is computed for every QoI $_j$ from the set $\mathcal{Q}_{\text{a priori}}$ defined in the previous paragraph using

$$\text{MSE}_j = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\tilde{Y}_{i,\text{true}}^j - \tilde{Y}_{i,\text{pred}}^j \right)^2, \quad (5)$$

with n being the number of observations in the validation dataset and \tilde{Y}_i^j being the scaled mass fraction of j th QoI for observation i , such that every mass fraction \tilde{Y}_j is scaled to the $\langle -1, 1 \rangle$ -range. This scaling is applied to every QoI to standardize the MSE metric and make it comparable. To get the final MSE metric, the average over all the QoIs is computed with $\text{MSE} = 1/m \sum_{j=1}^m \text{MSE}_j$.

2.4.2. A posteriori simulation assessment

Once the PV was evolved over time using the PV source term model and the thermo-chemical state-space was reconstructed using the full state-space model, we evaluated the quality of the ROM simulation by measuring the relative error on the predicted maximum value $\varepsilon_{i,j}^{\text{max}}$ for QoI $_j$ of test trajectory i , possibly corresponding to peaks occurring during ignition, and

the predicted steady-state value $\varepsilon_{i,j}^{\text{SS}}$, *i.e.*, the difference between the true and predicted value at the end of the trajectory i for QoI_j . The two metrics are defined as following:

$$\varepsilon_{i,j}^{\text{max}} = \frac{|\max_t Y_{i,\text{true}}^j(t) - \max_t Y_{i,\text{pred}}^j(t)|}{|\max_t Y_{i,\text{true}}^j(t)|} \quad (6)$$

$$\varepsilon_{i,j}^{\text{SS}} = \frac{|Y_{i,\text{true}}^j(t_{\text{end}}) - Y_{i,\text{pred}}^j(t_{\text{end}})|}{|\max_t Y_{i,\text{true}}^j(t)|} \quad (7)$$

with $Y_{i,\text{true}}^j(t)$ the true QoI_j value of test trajectory i at timestep t and $Y_{i,\text{pred}}^j(t)$ the predicted one.

3. Numerical setup

3.1. The test case and the heuristic PVs used

The main dataset used to demonstrate the encoder-decoder modifications and associated observations, as well as for the *a priori* and *a posteriori* evaluation of the parameterizations comes from homogeneous, closed reactor (autoignition) simulations of a premixed hydrogen flame. The premixed autoignition dataset was generated with simulations of an isochoric, adiabatic, and closed homogeneous reactor using Cantera (32) and Spitfire (33). The chemical reaction mechanism developed by Glarborg *et al.* (34) was used, which focuses on NO_x formation and contains 21 species and 109 reactions. The dataset consists of 100 simulations starting with an initial temperature T_0 of 900K and equally-spaced mixture fractions ranging from 0.015 to 0.035, corresponding to equivalence ratios from 0.52 to 1.23. Therefore, the dataset contains the conditions where NO_x formation is maximum ($\phi = 0.6\text{--}0.7$) as

well as the conditions where the highest temperatures are reached near stoichiometry. Overall, the dataset of 100 simulations contains 242k observations used for the *a posteriori* simulations. For the training and evaluation of the optimized PV, every other simulation was selected, resulting in 121k observations. In both cases, the dataset is dense enough to represent well the complete range of operating conditions.

A flamelet dataset was used as a second dataset to show that the findings generalize to a more complex case. This dataset covers similar conditions to the autoignition dataset. The freely-propagating flat flame of a premixed hydrogen-air mixture was also generated with Cantera (32) using the mechanism developed by Glarborg (34). The dataset consists of 71 simulations starting with an initial temperature T_0 of 300K and pressure p_0 of 1atm and equally-spaced equivalence ratios ranging from 0.35 to 0.7, chosen to cover the region where NO_x formation is maximum. To fully capture this region, a domain length of 0.3m was chosen. Next, the Soret effect and multicomponent transport were included for the simulation. This resulted in a flamelet dataset of 32k observations.

The heuristic PV defined by experts is commonly composed of the main reactants and products to track the progress of the combustion process (24). Hence, we used in this paper $Y_{\text{PV}} = Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} - Y_{\text{H}_2} - Y_{\text{O}_2}$ as the main heuristic PV which is a common choice for hydrogen combustion (35; 36), where Y_i is the mass fraction of species i . Two other heuristic PVs were considered to better capture auxiliary processes of the hydrogen combustion next to the main combustion, *i.e.*, $Y_{\text{PV}} = Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} + w Y_{\text{HO}_2}$ (37; 38) and $Y_{\text{PV}} = Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} + w Y_{\text{NO}}$ (8), with w being a weight to be determined for each dataset. No standard

method exists to determine the weight since it depends on the dataset and the distribution of the mass fraction. In Naud *et al.* (37) and Göktolga *et al.* (38), they assigned respectively a weight of 10 and 1000 to HO_2 . Alternatively, in Schepers and Van Oijen (39) and Almutairi *et al.* (40) the inverse of the molecular weight was used as weight for each species in the PV definition. Hence, to make the comparison with the optimized PV as fair as possible, we selected for each heuristic PV and each dataset the weight from the set $\{1, 2, 10, 100, 1000\}$ for which the heuristic f -PV parameterization had the lowest average cost, which corresponded to the lowest or nearly lowest average MSE. For the autoignition dataset, $Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} + 10 Y_{\text{HO}_2}$ and $Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} + Y_{\text{NO}}$ provided the best manifold parameterizations and $Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} + 1000 Y_{\text{HO}_2}$ and $Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} + 1000 Y_{\text{NO}}$ for the flamelet dataset, with the complete analysis on the determination of the weights provided in Sections S2.1.1 and S2.2.1 of the supplementary material. The rationale behind the set of candidate weights being equal to or larger than unity comes from the fact that the mass fractions Y_{HO_2} and Y_{NO} are smaller than those of $Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$. Therefore, the weight should be large enough to ensure that the minor species has a significant contribution in the PV with respect to H_2O .

3.2. Training of the QoI-aware encoder-decoder

The encoder-decoder was implemented in PyTorch (41) and used similar hyperparameters to the ones defined in previous work (13), provided in Table 2. We used the Adam optimizer (42) with an initial learning rate of 0.025, decreased gradually to 0.00025 at the end of the training with a cosine decay scheduler. The training lasted 100k epochs without minibatching (11; 13) to consider the complete manifold at every weight update. To match the sym-

metry of the decoder’s hyperbolic tangent activation function, f was scaled between -0.5 and 0.5 and the PV was lifted to -0.0005 and 0.0005 whenever the PV range fell below 0.001 to avoid the PV range shrinking over the iterations. This means that the encoder weights w_i are rescaled when the PV range drops below this threshold. Compared to the previous work (13), the PV is not rescaled at every iteration to reduce the intervention to a minimum and converged naturally to the range 1–10, which was found to be beneficial. The important major and minor species, along with key NO_x species, are transformed to the logarithmic scale (43; 44; 45) and selected as the primary quantities of interest (QoIs) to be captured by the f -PV parameterization, in addition to temperature and the PV source term. Therefore, in this paper, the set of chosen QoIs at the output of the decoder is defined as $\mathcal{Q} = \{T, \log(Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}_2}), \log(Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}), \log(Y_{\text{H}_2}), \log(Y_{\text{HO}_2}), \log(Y_{\text{N}_2\text{O}}), \log(Y_{\text{NO}_2}), \log(Y_{\text{NO}}), \log(Y_{\text{O}_2}), \log(Y_{\text{OH}}), \dot{\omega}_{\text{PV}}/\rho\}$ with the choice of applying the logarithm to the species explained in Section 4.2. The training of the encoder-decoder on an Intel Xeon E5-2630 v3 CPU (2.40 GHz) took approximately 2 hours for the autoignition dataset and approximately 40 minutes for the flamelet dataset. Finally, every encoder-decoder is trained ten times using different random seeds unless stated otherwise. We verified that the obtained optimized parameterizations were similar over the different random initializations. When reporting only the results of one optimized parameterization, we selected the parameterization obtained with the encoder-decoder having the lowest validation MSE during training, which did not systematically correspond to the best manifold topology in terms of cost function.

Hyperparameter	Encoder-decoder
Input scaling	None
PV scaling*	-0.0005 to 0.0005
f scaling	-0.5 to 0.5
Output scaling	-1 to 1
Batch size	Complete dataset
Validation percentage	20%
Neurons (hidden layers)	[11, 21, 21]
Activation function – scaling	linear
Activation function – encoder	linear
Activation function – hidden	$\tanh(\cdot)$
Activation function – output	$\tanh(\cdot)$
Bias weights	hidden & output layers
Distribution weight init. – scaling	$\mathcal{U}(1, 2)$
Distribution weight init. – encoder	$\mathcal{N}(0, 0.05^2)$
Distribution weight init. – decoder	$\mathcal{N}(0, 0.05^2)$
Random seed number	0 to 9
Optimizer	Adam
Learning rate (Lr.)	0.025-0.00025
Lr. scheduler	Cosine
Epochs	100000

Table 2: Hyperparameters for the training of the encoder-decoder. *PV scaling is performed at each iteration where the PV range has fallen below 0.001.

4. Effects of the encoder-decoder modifications and observations on the manifold topology

4.1. Trainable neural scaling layer aids in PV optimization

One key finding of this work comes from introducing the trainable neural scaling layer prior to the encoder, as described in Section 2.2. In this section, we illustrate the effect that the scaling layer has on optimizing the PV definition. We trained the encoder-decoder with several hyperparameter settings and random seeds, with and without the scaling layer. The hyperparameters being varied are the set of QoIs at the decoder being transformed to the logarithmic scale, described in more details in Section S1.1.1 of the supplementary material.

By measuring the parameterization quality with the MSE *vs.* the cost function on average for all QoIs and for the PV source term alone, Fig. 2a shows the effect of adding the neural scaling layer to the encoder-decoder on the manifold parameterization. We observe that adding the scaling layer improves the manifold quality for most QoIs as indicated by the lower average cost and MSE. On the contrary, Fig. 2b suggests that the PV source term is better parametrized without the scaling layer, with the PV source term cost, $\mathcal{L}_{\hat{\omega}_{PV}}$, ranging between 1 and 1.1 compared to 1.2 to 1.7 with the scaling layer. By visualizing the f -PV manifolds in Fig. 3, this difference is explained by the larger feature size of the PV source term when the scaling layer is excluded. Hence, the f -PV manifold obtained with the scaling layer is compressed in regions associated with the high PV source term values to stretch out other regions of the manifold where other QoIs are present, explaining the lower average cost. This will be further discussed in the next sections. For

transparency, Fig. S1 in the supplementary material shows Fig. 2 including the three outliers, which correspond to poor parameterizations resulting from unfavorable random initialization.

Fig. 2: Encoders-decoders with a trainable scaling layer yield improved f -PV parameterizations compared to those without it. Due to the stretching of the lower and upper manifold regions, the main feature size of the PV source term is reduced. (a) Average QoI cost, \mathcal{L}_{avg} , vs. the average MSE of all QoIs with and without the trainable scaling layer. (b) The PV source term cost, $\mathcal{L}_{\dot{\omega}_{\text{PV}}}$, vs. the average cost, \mathcal{L}_{avg} , with and without the trainable scaling layer.

Fig. 3: The f -PV manifold parametrized by an optimized PV obtained with an encoder-decoder including (b) the trainable scaling layer exhibits a compressed main feature size for the PV source term compared to the encoder-decoder excluding (a) the trainable scaling layer. In both cases, the scaling layer is the only difference between the two trainings. All other hyperparameter settings and the random seed are identical. The initial condition (IC) and the steady-state (SS) of the 0D trajectories, corresponding respectively to the bottom and top points of the manifold, are annotated on the right-hand side of the manifolds.

To understand the role of the scaling layer, we analyze the weight distribution for the hyperparameter set giving the best and most consistent parameterization, corresponding to the hyperparameters of the encoder-decoder

used in subsequent sections. Fig. 4a shows the encoder weights, w_i , of an encoder-decoder without the scaling layer *vs.* the scaled encoder weights, $s_i w_i$, of an encoder-decoder with a scaling layer for every input species i and random seed. Hence, the figure compares the total weight assigned to species i for the architecture excluding *vs.* including the scaling layer. Each point corresponds to one input species (19 in total) and one of the five random seeds used for training, resulting in 95 points overall. We observe that the weights coming from both architectures follow a similar trend. However, with the addition of the scaling layer, more extreme total weight values are reached. For $s_i w_i$ values above unity, more points are present under the bisector. Similarly for weights below unity, some total encoder weights with the scaling layer reach very small values below 10^{-10} with encoding weights being around 10^{-2} to 10^{-1} without scaling layer. This is shown in Fig. S2 of the supplementary material. These small weights are especially observed for H_2 and O_2 species. To avoid compressing the interesting range of datapoints between 10^{-3} to 10^4 , Fig. 4a has been zoomed-in where 90% of the datapoints lie. Hence, Fig. 4a with the five extreme points below 10^{-3} included and with species labels can be found in Section S1.1.3 of the supplementary material. From this analysis, we conclude that adding the scaling layer amplifies the contribution of important species and further suppresses irrelevant ones.

Continuing the weight analysis, we investigate how encoders-decoders with the scaling layer can reach more extreme total weights. Fig. 4b shows the encoder weights, w_i , against the individual scalings, s_i , for the architecture with the scaling layer. We notice that both quantities are generally of

the same order of magnitude. This means that the encoder-decoder with the scaling layer distributes the total weight over the two layers almost equally, to reach larger/smaller total weights compared to a single encoding layer. Introducing the trainable scaling layer gives the encoding operation an additional degree of freedom in how important specific species can be made in the PV definition. Moreover, a second mode is visible in Fig. 4b, where the scaling weight is around unity and only the encoder weight determines the importance of the species in the PV definition. In that case, the scaling layer does not contribute to defining the PV. This is explained by the current architecture depicted in Fig. 1 where there is no forced preference for which of the two layers acts as scaling *vs.* encoding. We hypothesize that the encoder-decoder’s choice to distribute the total weight between the two layers *vs.* to have all the weight magnitude accumulate in the encoding layer is arbitrary and depends on the weight initialization and gradient descent optimization process. In summary, the trainable scaling layer introduces more degrees of freedom to the encoder-decoder and helps find more consistently good parameterizations while being less sensitive to the selected subset of QoIs transformed to the log-scale. This is explained by the fact that the scaling layer helps to find better parameterizations since extreme weights are distributed over the two layers and therefore requires less weight updates during training. As a trade-off for the addition of the scaling layer, only one additional hyperparameter has to be tuned, *i.e.*, the choice of the random distribution for scaling weights initialization.

We hypothesize two reasons why this trainable scaling layer improves the training. First of all, it is well known that the increase in depth of a neural

network enhances its expressiveness (46) and larger models generalize better (47), since the model’s performance is proportional to the number of trainable parameters (48; 49). Secondly, it has been shown that stacking layers helps accelerating training. Gong *et al.* (50) showed how deep neural networks could be efficiently trained by progressively stacking layers. Similarly to our idea, Cao *et al.* (51) designed a “depthwise over-parametrized convolutional layer” with more parameters than a traditional convolutional layer, but which can be reduced to a traditional one. They showed that this layer improved the performance of convolutional neural networks without affecting the inference time since the over-parametrized layer can be re-parameterized to a traditional layer. Arora *et al.* (52) showed theoretically and experimentally that over-parameterizing a neural network by increasing the depth, even with a linear layer as in our work, helped to speed up the training of the neural network. Additionally, they mention that the addition of a linear layer does not affect the expressiveness of the neural network, but is simply an over-parametrization. Hence, we tend to favor the second reason. Nonetheless, further study will be required to fully understand the underlying mechanism through which the trainable scaling layer interacts with gradient descent.

Fig. 4: Encoders-decoders with the trainable scaling layer reach more extreme weights than ones without. These architectures with the trainable scaling layer distribute the weight equally between the scaling and encoder layers or a second mode appears where all the weight is assigned to the encoder. (a) The absolute encoder weights, w_i , for encoders-decoders without the scaling layer *vs.* the absolute total weights, $s_i w_i$, for encoders-decoders with the scaling layer for every species i and 5 random seeds. (b) The absolute scaling weights, s_i , *vs.* the absolute encoder weights, w_i , of encoders-decoders with the scaling layer for every species i and random seed.

4.2. *The effect of QoIs transformed to the logarithmic scale at the decoder’s output*

Compared to previous implementations of the encoder-decoder (11; 9; 12; 13; 10; 14; 25), the species’ mass fractions at the output of the decoder are transformed to the logarithmic scale instead of keeping them in the linear scale (28). This is physically motivated by the exponential dependence of chemical reaction rates on temperature described by the Arrhenius equation (53), thereby leading to high gradients in species mass fraction profiles.

Similarly as with the addition of the scaling layer, employing the logarithmic transformation of the QoIs has the effect of compressing the ignition region, corresponding to the interior part of the manifold, and stretching out the extremities of the manifold as illustrated in Fig. 5b. In this case, it can be intuitively explained by the fact that H_2O_2 , HO_2 , NO , and NO_2 are respectively present near the bottom and upper boundaries of the manifold. Specifically, H_2O_2 and HO_2 are pre-ignition species present near initial conditions (ICs), and NO and NO_2 are formed by slow reactions and therefore present near the chemical equilibrium, or steady-state (SS) region. By applying the logarithmic scale to all the QoIs, the above-mentioned species are the most affected as they exhibit high gradients near IC and SS on unoptimized manifold topologies. With the logarithmic transformation, their gradients in the compressed region are artificially increased, shown in Section S1.2 of the supplementary material for H_2O_2 . Therefore, during training, the encoder-decoder will focus more on these regions and consequently a larger portion of the optimized PV will be dedicated to these manifold regions, as shown in Fig. 5b for Y_{NO_2} and Y_{HO_2} . Notably, for this dataset, applying a logarithmic

transformation only to H_2O_2 or HO_2 , while keeping the other mass fractions linear at the decoder, resulted in optimized manifolds comparable to those obtained when all mass fractions were logarithmically scaled. This is due to the main manifold improvement being near the IC when switching from the linear scale to the logarithmic scale, which is achievable with either H_2O_2 or HO_2 alone in the logarithmic scale.

To quantify the effect of the change of scale, we computed the MSE and cost for every QoI for the best encoder-decoder optimization with the QoIs in the linear *vs.* logarithmic scales. From Fig. 5a, we observe an MSE improvement of one or multiple orders of magnitude for all QoIs by applying the logarithmic transformation on the species' mass fractions at the decoder's output. H_2O_2 , HO_2 , NO , and NO_2 gain the most advantage from the log-transformation as features described by those species become stretched out on the manifold and therefore easier to reconstruct with an ANN. The increase in cost for the other QoIs is explained by the compression of the interior part of the manifold (corresponding to the ignition region) which decreases the main feature size of these QoIs. Nonetheless, the MSE decreases for these QoIs as it allows the ANN to improve the prediction of values near IC and SS without sacrificing accuracy for values around ignition. Overall, this indicates that we are willing to compress the main feature size to have the full trajectory well captured by the PV and hence facilitating the regression over the complete range of values.

Fig. 5: The encoder-decoder with the QoIs at the decoder’s output in the logarithmic scale improve the f -PV parameterization compared to the ones with the QoIs in the linear scale by stretching out all key manifold regions. (a) Cost and MSE for every QoI comparing both parameterizations. The QoIs are displayed from top to bottom in decreasing order of $\Delta_{\text{MSE}} = \log(|\text{MSE}_{\text{linear QoI}} - \text{MSE}_{\text{log(QoI)}}|)$, corresponding to the length of the black line. (b) The f -PV manifolds for both parameterizations colored by Y_{NO_2} , Y_{HO_2} , and $Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$.

4.3. Sparsifying the optimized PV definition

Usually, a heuristic PV is only composed of one or a few species (24; 8). However, for a parameterization obtained with an encoder-decoder, the PV is a linear combination of all species included at the input, being 19 species for our dataset, with various relative contribution. In previous works, sparsity of the PV definition has been mentioned without detailed investigation. For example, Perry *et al.* (9) promoted sparsity in the PV definition by adding an L1 norm on the encoder weights in the loss function. The optimized PVs contained typically only one or two species in their definitions. However, this work did not investigate the effect of introducing the L1 norm term on the quality of the optimized PV. More recently, Zdybał *et al.* (13) observed

that most species did not contribute to the optimized PV definition without investigating it further.

To investigate the effect of imposing sparse definitions of the optimized PVs, we removed step-wisely the least important species from the PV definition, *i.e.*, the current species with the lowest $\max(|w_i s_i| \cdot Y_i)$. We measured at every step the cost and MSE on average for all QoIs and also specifically for the PV source term. The results are given in Fig. 6a showing that the removal of many species from the PV definition does not affect the manifold topology. Keeping only H₂O, HO₂, NO, H, and H₂O₂ in the PV definition gives effectively the same manifold as having all 19 species included in the definition as the MSE and the cost value do not substantially change. From this set of species defining the sparse optimized PV, the encoder-decoder has identified H₂O as the most important species, which is also typically used as heuristic PV for hydrogen combustion (54). The reason is that H₂O is a good indicator of the overall combustion reaction progress. Next to H₂O, the encoder-decoder has refined the optimized PV definition with minor species and NO to capture the different regions we are interested in, defined by the set of species at the decoder’s output. The optimized PV incorporates HO₂ and H₂O₂ to represent the low-temperature pre-ignition chemistry, the H atom known as the principal indicator of the high-temperature ignition region, representing the activity of the broader radical pool (H, O, OH). Additionally, NO is included to track the primary NO_x formation pathway (34; 8). Note that the obtained optimized PV is tuned for this specific dataset and the optimized PV definition only holds for thermochemical conditions similar to the training dataset.

We further explain the presence of HO_2 and NO from a topological point-of-view. In Fig. 6a, once H_2O_2 is removed from the sparse PV definition, the average MSE and the MSE of the PV source term both begin to increase. The average cost starts to drastically increase to 17 when NO is removed, while the cost for the PV source term decreases. This is explained in Fig. 6b where f -PV manifolds parametrized by the most important species $\{Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}, Y_{\text{HO}_2}, Y_{\text{NO}}\}$, $\{Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}, Y_{\text{HO}_2}\}$ and $\{Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}\}$ are colored by Y_{NO} , $Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}_2}$ and $\dot{\omega}_{\text{PV}}$. When Y_{NO} is removed from the sparse PV definition, the top part of the manifold gets compressed and the PV definition becomes non-unique in that region. As explained earlier, this manifold area corresponds to the region near SS where most NO_x is present due to its long formation time-scale. Hence, the removal of Y_{NO} induces an expansion of the large PV source terms towards the upper region of the manifold explaining the reduction in its cost. When removing the second most important species from the sparse optimized PV, *i.e.*, the pre-ignition species Y_{HO_2} , and keeping thus only $Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ in the PV, the bottom part of the manifold gets compressed, corresponding to the region near ICs where HO_2 and H_2O_2 are present. As a consequence of the HO_2 removal, the PV source term is further expanded towards the bottom, leading to a further decrease of the PV source term cost, and a compression of the H_2O_2 feature size. The compression of regions near IC and SS are detrimental to the manifold parameterization illustrated by the drastic increase in MSE for all species and the PV source term. The decreasing PV source term cost, when removing the third and subsequently the second most important species from the PV definition, comes from the increasing main feature size since the cost metric rewards large feature sizes while it does not penalize the gradient in the

important but small PV source terms, like the MSE metric, when observing the PV source term in the linear scale. For what concerns the average cost when the second most important species is removed, the average cost drops from 17 to 7 due to the non-uniqueness near SS being resolved, but high gradients are appearing near IC, next to the high gradients already present near SS, which keeps the cost high. The drop in average cost is discussed in more detail in Section S1.3 of the supplementary material. Nonetheless, in both cases, the large average costs indicate that the manifold is not well parametrized. These results show that the optimized PV is inherently defined by only a few, but crucial species which are responsible for the topology improvements with respect to heuristic manifold parameterizations.

Fig. 6: The optimized PV definition can be sparsified to five species without altering the manifold topology. Removing the most important species from the definition compresses key manifold regions. (a) Evolution of the MSE and cost for all QoIs (top row) and for the PV source term alone (bottom row) when sparsifying the optimized PV. The species are ordered from the least important one on the left to the most important one on the right. At each step the cost and MSE are re-computed when removing the next least important species from the optimized PV definition. (b) The f -PV manifolds parametrized by sparsified optimized PVs containing only the three, two, or single most important species, colored by Y_{NO} , $Y_{H_2O_2}$, and $\dot{\omega}_{PV}$.

5. A priori analysis: The heuristic *vs.* the optimized PV

5.1. The autoignition dataset

With the optimal encoder-decoder architecture and hyperparameters discussed in previous sections for the optimized PV, *i.e.*, addition of a scaling layer and the logarithmic transformation of QoIs at the decoder, we compare *a priori* the quality of manifolds parametrized by the optimized *vs.* the dif-

ferent heuristic PVs for the autoignition dataset. As described in section 3.1, the heuristic PVs are defined as $Y_{\text{PV}} = Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} - Y_{\text{H}_2} - Y_{\text{O}_2}$, $Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} + 10 Y_{\text{HO}_2}$, and $Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} + Y_{\text{NO}}$ according to expert knowledge and optimizing the weight for the two latter.

Fig. 7 compares the different heuristic and optimized PVs employing the MSE and the cost function for every QoI. Similarly as was seen in Fig. 5 when comparing encoders-decoders with linear *vs.* logarithmic decoded QoIs, the MSE of all QoIs decreases with a few orders of magnitude when we use the optimized PV as opposed to the heuristic ones. The largest improvements are obtained for the minor species, *i.e.*, NO, NO₂, N₂O, OH, HO₂, and H₂O₂. The cost for the major species like H₂, O₂ and H₂O, which are spread over the complete manifold, slightly increases with the optimized parameterization due to the decrease in main feature size, shown in Fig. 8. Nonetheless, the MSE still improves for these QoIs using the optimized parameterization. Comparing the different heuristic PVs, $Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} - Y_{\text{H}_2} - Y_{\text{O}_2}$ shows average performance on all QoIs, while $Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} + 10 Y_{\text{HO}_2}$ performs better for species located at the lower manifold region like HO₂, and H₂O₂ and $Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} + Y_{\text{NO}}$ for NO_x species. For example, the upper region of the manifold is stretched out for $Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} + Y_{\text{NO}}$ in Fig. 8c to better parametrize the NO_x species present in that manifold region. Overall, the optimized PV yields a superior manifold compared to the heuristic PVs, with the average cost, \mathcal{L}_{avg} , being 0.35 for the optimized parameterization, 2.38 for $Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} - Y_{\text{H}_2} - Y_{\text{O}_2}$, 6.17 for $Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} + 10 Y_{\text{HO}_2}$ and 2.32 for $Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} + Y_{\text{NO}}$. This is explained by the manifold improvements both near IC and SS resulting from the optimized PV, highlighted in previous sections, whereas those regions on a manifold are

compressed when parametrized by the heuristic PVs. In the supplementary material, the differences in manifold parameterizations are further illustrated in Section S2.1.2 and we elaborate more on the origin of the QoI regression improvements in Section S3.4. Additionally, we show in Section S2.1.3 of the supplementary material that the optimized parametrization is superior to manifold parameterizations obtained employing PCA similarly as reported in previous works (11; 9; 25; 13).

Given the importance of the PV source term parameterization to obtain an accurate ROM, we illustrate in Fig. 8a, Fig. 8d and Fig. 9 the qualitative and quantitative differences between the heuristic defined by $Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} - Y_{\text{H}_2} - Y_{\text{O}_2}$ and the optimized parameterization for this QoI. From Fig. 8a, Fig. 8d and Fig. 9, it is clear that the optimized PV leads to a smaller main feature size in the PV source term due to the regions near IC and SS being stretched out. This results in a shift of the main peak to the left for the \hat{D} -curve (see section 2.4.1), as shown in Fig. 9b, leading to a slightly larger cost, *i.e.*, 1.34 instead of 1.03 for the optimized and heuristic PV, respectively. Next, comparing the PVs for the same trajectory in the logarithmic scale in Fig. 9c, we observe that the heuristic PV source term increases steeply near the manifold boundaries making it later more difficult to regress during ROM simulations. This is confirmed by a cost of 28.8 for the heuristic PV source term in the logarithmic scale illustrated with the \hat{D} -curve in Fig. 9d. On the contrary, owing to the manifold improvements near IC and SS, the PV source term of the optimized PV starts and ends at high values and has a smoother transition towards the largest source term values. As a consequence, the \hat{D} -curve of the PV source term in the logarithmic scale exhibits a single peak

and thus the cost is reduced with one order of magnitude with respect to the heuristic PV, *i.e.*, 2.87. We conclude that the optimized PV is *a priori* better suited than the heuristic PV to perform accurate ROM simulations owing to the manifold being stretched in crucial regions (near IC and SS), which can especially help start and terminate the simulation accurately. As a result, we observe that the small PV source term values near IC are better parametrized by the optimized PV, essential to accurately predict the ignition time.

Fig. 7: The manifold parametrized by the optimized PV achieves *a priori* a lower MSE for every QoI than the ones parametrized by the heuristic PVs defined by $Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} - Y_{\text{H}_2} - Y_{\text{O}_2}$, $Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} + 10 Y_{\text{HO}_2}$, and $Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} + Y_{\text{NO}}$. Additionally, the optimized PV improves the manifold parameterization for NO, NO₂, HO₂, and H₂O₂ with respect to the cost while minimally degrading the parameterization for the other QoIs by increasing their main feature size. The QoIs are displayed from top to bottom in decreasing order of $\Delta_{\text{MSE}} = \log(|\text{MSE}_{\text{Heu.}} - \text{MSE}_{\text{Opt.}}|)$, corresponding to the length of the black line.

Fig. 8: The optimized manifold parameterization (d) has a smaller feature size for the PV source term compared to the heuristic parameterizations defined by $Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} - Y_{\text{H}_2} - Y_{\text{O}_2}$ (a), $Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} + 10 Y_{\text{HO}_2}$ (b), and $Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} + 10 Y_{\text{NO}}$ (c). The dashed lines for the heuristic PV defined by $Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} - Y_{\text{H}_2} - Y_{\text{O}_2}$ and the optimized PV correspond to the trajectory shown in Figs. 9a and c

Fig. 9: The optimized parameterization has a larger main feature size for the PV source term in the linear scale than the heuristic parameterization, defined by $Y_{H_2O} - Y_{H_2} - Y_{O_2}$. The compression of the main feature size for the optimized parameterization allows the full range of PV source term scales to be well parametrized on the contrary of the heuristic parameterization. (a) Evolution of the PV source term in the linear scale along a PV trajectory (marked with a dashed line in the f -PV manifolds in Figs. 8a and d). To compare the heuristic and optimized PV source term, they have been rescaled to the same range. (b) \hat{D} -curve of the PV source term in the linear scale parametrized by the heuristic and optimized PV. (c) Evolution of the PV source term in the logarithmic scale along a PV trajectory (marked with a dashed line in the f -PV manifolds). (d) \hat{D} -curve of the PV source term in the logarithmic scale parametrized by the heuristic and optimized PV.

5.2. The flamelet dataset

To demonstrate that the findings discussed in Section 4 generalize to a more complex case, the same encoder-decoder architecture is applied on a flamelet dataset described in Section 3.1. The only difference with the autoignition case is the use of both the species mass fractions in the linear and logarithmic scale at the output of the decoder instead of only in the

logarithmic scale. Fig. 10 compares the heuristic parameterization defined by $Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} - Y_{\text{H}_2} - Y_{\text{O}_2}$ with the optimized parameterization. Similarly as for the autoignition case, the encoder-decoder succeeds to stretch out the targeted manifold regions yielding a lower MSE and cost for most QoIs. Due to the stretching of regions where minor species are located, QoIs exhibiting a main feature size spread over the complete manifold, *e.g.*, HO_2 , O_2 , H_2 , and temperature, have a reduced cost. Nonetheless, the MSE decreases also for these QoIs meaning that the reduction in main feature size is not detrimental for the regression. For clarity, only the heuristic PV defined as $Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} - Y_{\text{H}_2} - Y_{\text{O}_2}$ is shown. The interested reader is referred to Section S2.2.2 of the supplementary material for the results of the other heuristic PVs.

In Section S2.2.3 of the supplementary material, we show that the findings discussed in Section 4 still hold. The encoder-decoder with trainable scaling layer provides a better optimized parameterization compared to without when varying the set of QoIs at the decoder’s output and random seed. Secondly, adding all species mass fractions in the logarithmic scale to the set of species in the linear scale at the decoder’s output helps to obtain better manifold topologies. Note that the optimal set of QoIs at the decoder’s output will not always contain all species in the logarithmic scale since it depends on the distribution of the species mass fractions. Finally, we observed that the optimized PV definition could be sparsified to 9 species for this case.

Fig. 10: The optimized parameterization achieves a lower MSE and cost compared to the heuristic one, $Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} - Y_{\text{H}_2} - Y_{\text{O}_2}$, owing to the stretching of the key manifold regions. (a) Cost and MSE for every QoI comparing *a priori* the heuristic and optimized manifold parameterizations. The QoIs are displayed from top to bottom in decreasing order of $\Delta_{\text{MSE}} = \log(|\text{MSE}_{\text{Heu.}} - \text{MSE}_{\text{Opt.}}|)$, corresponding to the length of the black line. (b) f -PV manifolds using the heuristic PV, defined as $Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} - Y_{\text{H}_2} - Y_{\text{O}_2}$, and the optimized PV colored by N₂O, OH, and H₂O. The results for the other heuristic parameterizations can be found in Section S2.2.2 of the supplementary material.

6. *A posteriori* analysis: The heuristic *vs.* the optimized PV

The goal of this *a posteriori* analysis is to observe the effect of the manifold topology differences between different heuristic and optimized PVs on the accuracy of ROM simulations for the 0D case. The PVs are tested on ten equally-spaced trajectories (each for a fixed f value), not being part of the training dataset, shown in Fig. 11 for the optimized manifold parameterization.

Fig. 11: The f -PV manifold parametrized with the optimized PV showing the ten test trajectories where the *a posteriori* simulations are performed. The red dashed line shows the fifth test trajectory for which the *a posteriori* results are shown in Section 6. The results for the other test trajectories can be found in Section S3 of the supplementary material.

6.1. Evolving the PV over time

To perform the ROM simulation, the PV is evolved over time using a regression model that predicts the PV source term, as explained in Section 2.3. For this purpose, one ANN for each parameterization is trained on the training dataset and is hereafter referred to as the PV source term model. Figs. 12 show how well all PV source term models can predict *a priori* pointwisely each PV source term value of the fifth test trajectory. From this figure, we conclude that the PV source term model parametrized by the optimized PV is in general more accurate for $t = 0$ s to $t = 0.05$ s and also near the end of the trajectory. These results are in agreement with the *a priori* observations in Section 5.1. The PV source term model for the optimized PV benefits from the optimized manifold parameterization being stretched out near IC and SS making these regions easier to regress. To rule out the ANN architecture as

the source of the lower accuracy observed for the heuristic PV models, we tested larger ANN architectures, *e.g.*, four hidden layers with [30, 50, 50, 50] neurons. However, these larger ANNs did not improve the accuracy of the heuristic PV models. Additionally, we performed the *a posteriori* analysis with tabulation instead of ANNs and observed the same trend of a higher accuracy with the optimized parameterization over the heuristic parameterization, illustrated in Section S3.8 of the supplementary material. This shows that the compressed small PV source terms are intrinsically challenging to model. The *a priori* accuracy of the PV source term models for the other test trajectories showed similar trends as in Fig. 12 and can be found in Section S3.2 of the supplementary material.

Fig. 12: The PV source term model parametrized by the optimized PV (d) predicts *a priori* more accurately the true PV source term compared to the ROMs parametrized by the heuristic PVs defined by $Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} - Y_{\text{H}_2} - Y_{\text{O}_2}$ (a), $Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} + 10 Y_{\text{HO}_2}$ (b), and $Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} + 10 Y_{\text{NO}}$ (c) for the fifth test trajectory of the autoignition manifold. The difference in accuracy is explained by the distribution of PV source term values. The *a priori* performance of the PV source term models for the other trajectories can be found in Section S3.2 of the supplementary material.

Initializing the PVs at $t = 0$ s and employing the PV source term models for all parameterizations to evolve the PV over time, gives in Fig. 13

the predicted PV trajectories against the fifth true test trajectory obtained with the full-order model (FOM). We observe that the ROM parametrized by the optimized PV predicts almost perfectly the ignition time with a delay of 0.005s, corresponding to 5.2% of the ignition time, while the ROMs parametrized by the heuristic PVs have a larger delay of 0.41s and 0.03s for $Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} - Y_{\text{H}_2} - Y_{\text{O}_2}$ and $Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} + 10 Y_{\text{HO}_2}$ respectively, corresponding to 414% and 27% of the ignition time. The same trend is observed for the other test trajectories with delays in the same order of magnitude for both with a minimum and maximum relative error in ignition time prediction of 408% to 570% and 19% to 35% for the heuristic PVs mentioned previously and 0.15% to 6.9% for the optimized PV. For the heuristic PV defined by $Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} + Y_{\text{NO}}$, no ignition is observed during the first two seconds of the simulation and this PV is therefore not considered in the rest of the *a posteriori* analysis. Similarly, we observed no ignition for the heuristic PV defined as $Y_{\text{PV}} = Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$, shown in Sections S3.2 and S3.3 of the supplementary material. The heuristic PV defined as $Y_{\text{PV}} = Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ was included in the supplementary material for completeness of the *a posteriori* analysis, but was not considered for the remainder of this work since it did not provide substantial additional insight compared to the other heuristic PVs considered.

We explain this difference in accuracy to predict the ignition between the PVs by the *a priori* accuracy of the PV source term models in predicting the PV source term from initial conditions till ignition, which itself originates from the difference in manifold topology, as discussed previously. For the PV models of the heuristic PVs, we observed in Fig. 12 an underprediction of the PV source term from $t = 0\text{s}$ to $t = 0.05\text{s}$ due to this manifold re-

gion being compressed and therefore more difficult to regress. During the ROM simulation, these errors on the PV source term accumulate over time explaining the large delay in ignition prediction for the heuristic PV trajectory in Fig. 13, with a comprehensive analysis on the error accumulation provided in Section S3.5 of the supplementary material. Hence, the ignition time delay is proportional to the underprediction of the PV source term, which is itself dependent on how well the manifold has been stretched out near IC. The heuristic manifold parametrized by $Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} + 10 Y_{\text{HO}_2}$ stretches slightly the manifold region from IC till ignition explaining the improved ignition time prediction compared to $Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} - Y_{\text{H}_2} - Y_{\text{O}_2}$. Similarly, both heuristic parametrizations defined by $Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} + Y_{\text{NO}}$ and $Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ exhibit very steep gradients near IC for the PV source term, resulting in the PV source term model failing to predict accurately the PV source term values in this region, thereby leading to no ignition when evolving the PV over time. The same rationale holds for the optimized PV, *i.e.*, the manifold being stretched out near ICs facilitates regression of the small PV source terms and hence leads to a more accurate prediction of the ignition time.

We note that we run the ROM simulations until $t = 2\text{s}$, which is longer than the original FOM simulations, lasting around 0.1-0.2s, for two reasons. First, the heuristic PV defined by $Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} - Y_{\text{H}_2} - Y_{\text{O}_2}$ has a long ignition time delay and the ignition is not always visible on the original time length of the trajectories. Extending the simulations makes it possible to visualize the heuristic PV ignition of $Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} - Y_{\text{H}_2} - Y_{\text{O}_2}$. Secondly, ROM simulations can suffer from leaving the manifold near the SS, instead of exhibiting an attractor state that should terminate the trajectory in the thermodynamic

limit. Therefore, we demonstrate here that the PV source terms predicted by both models are small enough that the predicted PV trajectory stays close to the true trajectory even in the much extended simulation.

Zdybał *et al.* (13) initiated the ROM simulation with various heuristic and optimized PVs at $t_0 = 9.5 \cdot 10^{-5}$ because their PV source term models could not accurately predict the near-zero PV source term near IC due to the manifold topology near the boundary. In contrast, in this work, we were able to start the ROM simulation from $t = 0$ s thanks to the three modifications in the training of the PV source term model, *i.e.*, the input manifold of the PV source term model was transformed to a rectangular shape, the model predicted the PV source terms in the logarithmic scale, and the ANN architecture of the model was larger than the one for the encoder-decoder. All these steps had the same purpose of increasing the prediction accuracy of the small PV source terms and are described in more detail in Section 2.3.

Fig. 13: The reduced-order model (ROM), evolving the PV over time employing the ANN PV source term model, parametrized by the optimized PV (d) predicts more accurately the true trajectory obtained by the full-order model (FOM) compared to the ROMs parametrized by the heuristic PVs defined by $Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} - Y_{\text{H}_2} - Y_{\text{O}_2}$ (a), $Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} + 10 Y_{\text{HO}_2}$ (b), and $Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} + 10 Y_{\text{NO}}$ (c) for the fifth test trajectory of the autoignition manifold. The difference in ignition time delay is explained by the accuracy of the PV source term models shown in Fig.12 which is itself a consequence of the manifold topology. The prediction of the PV trajectories for the other test trajectories can be found in Section S3.3 of the supplementary material.

6.2. Reconstructing the QoIs given f and the evolved PV

After evolving the PV over time with the PV source term model, the original state-space is reconstructed with the full state-space model described in Section 2.3. Three full state-space models are trained till convergence with a final validation MSE of 4.3×10^{-4} , 4.3×10^{-4} and 6.4×10^{-6} using the heuristic parameterizations defined by $Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} - Y_{\text{H}_2} - Y_{\text{O}_2}$ and $Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} + 10 Y_{\text{HO}_2}$ and the optimized parameterization respectively. This difference in training accuracy also agrees with the *a priori* observations in Section 5.1 and provides further evidence that smoothing the QoI gradients in the manifold parametrized by the optimized PV facilitates regression.

Applying the full state-space models on the evolved PV trajectory, we compare in Fig. 14 the reconstructed QoIs obtained from the ROMs parametrized

by the heuristic PVs and optimized PV against the FOM simulations, specifically here for the fifth test trajectory. For the other test trajectories, the reader is referred to Section S3.6 of the supplementary material. The ROM parametrized by the optimized PV matches closely the FOM. Conversely, the ROMs parametrized by the heuristic PVs fail to predict accurately all the species and the temperature. We observe three types of errors for these ROMs, *i.e.*, a delay in ignition, an inaccurate peak prediction at ignition for species such as HO₂ and OH and an offset at SS for NO₂ and NO, with the first type of error caused by the PV source term model and the two latter by the full state-space model. Nevertheless, they all originate from the poor manifold parameterization discussed in Section 5.1.

To quantify the two latter errors arising from the full state-space model, we visualize the distribution of $\varepsilon_{i,j}^{\max}$ and $\varepsilon_{i,j}^{\text{SS}}$, introduced in Section 2.4.2, over all test trajectories in Fig. 15. For all QoIs, the ROM parametrized by the optimized PV performs on average better than the ROMs parametrized by the heuristic PVs. We observe the largest differences for the species which are compressed in the manifold parametrized by the heuristic PVs, *i.e.*, radicals such as HO₂ near IC and NO_x species present near SS. Unexpectedly, the difference in prediction accuracy for NO₂ is less pronounced on both metrics despite gradients in NO₂ being highly compressed in the heuristic manifold.

To further illustrate that the manifold quality of the optimized PV is not affected by the sparse PV definition, already discussed *a priori* in Section 4.3, we performed the same ROM simulation by re-training the PV source term model and full state-space model with the sparsified optimized PV at the input instead of the full definition. We found that the ROM accuracy did not

significantly change by using the sparse definition of the optimized PV. For example, the maximal absolute time offset of the ignition prediction stayed in the same order of magnitude, *i.e.*, 0.005s *vs.* 0.008s for the sparsified and full optimized PV respectively. Further evidence is provided in Section S3.7 of the supplementary material.

Ultimately, the *a posteriori* results confirm the *a priori* observations. We observed *a priori* a superior manifold topology with the optimized parameterization and this led to a more accurate ROM. Moreover, these results show the importance of having the complete range of PV source term values till ignition and all QoIs well captured by the PV to be able to build an accurate ROM.

Fig. 14: The ROM parametrized by the optimized PV is more accurate than the ROMs parametrized by the heuristic PVs defined by $Y_{H_2O} - Y_{H_2} - Y_{O_2}$ and $Y_{H_2O} + 10 Y_{HO_2}$ for the prediction of the species and temperature of the fifth test trajectory as a consequence of the manifold topology improvements. The comparison for the other test trajectories can be found in Section S3.6 of the supplementary material.

Fig. 15: The optimized PV achieves a higher accuracy on the prediction of the max value and the relative error compared to the heuristic parameterizations defined by $Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} - Y_{\text{H}_2} - Y_{\text{O}_2}$ and $Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} + 10 Y_{\text{HO}_2}$. Distribution of the relative error on max value $\varepsilon_{i,j}^{\max}$ and relative error on the steady-state value $\varepsilon_{i,j}^{\text{SS}}$, introduced in Section 2.4.2, over all ten test trajectories for both ROMs parametrized by the heuristic and optimized PV.

7. Conclusion

Projection-based ROMs have become a promising modeling approach to optimize and design engineering systems at a reduced computational cost. To build such ROMs, the encoding-decoding architecture has gained increased attention for its ability to optimize the low-dimensional parameterization of high-dimensional systems with respect to user-defined QoIs, including QoIs that are functions of the projection operator. Several successful implementations of building a ROM based on the optimized parameterization provided by the encoder-decoder exist in the literature. However, there lacks a formal analysis to understand how an optimized parameterization, obtained with the encoder-decoder, improves the ROM simulation results compared to a heuristic parameterization in the context of reacting flow simulation.

Hence, we compared in this work both *a priori* and *a posteriori* different heuristic parameterizations, based on expert knowledge, *vs.* an optimized parameterization obtained with the encoder-decoder, for a hydrogen flame dataset. In the *a priori* analysis, we observed that the encoder-decoder was able to find an optimized parameterization that represents well all the decoded QoIs by stretching out the manifold topology in regions close to manifold boundaries, *i.e.*, corresponding to initial conditions and steady states. As a result, the QoI gradients were reduced in crucial regions whose topology dictate the amount of error induced at the start of simulation and the successful termination of the simulation. These manifold improvements facilitated the regression of the QoIs and led to a more accurate ROM simulation with the optimized parameterization compared to the heuristic ones.

To further improve the optimized parameterization obtained by the encoder-decoder, we introduced two novel concepts. Specifically, we added a trainable neural scaling layer prior to the encoder and we logarithmically transformed all species mass fractions reconstructed at the decoder. The trainable scaling layer provided additional degrees of freedom to the encoder-decoder allowing to assign more extreme total weights to the important input features. On the other hand, we found the optimal scaling for the decoded QoIs using prior knowledge on the process. The logarithmic transformation increased artificially the QoI gradients, which was especially important for the species formed in the vicinity of manifold boundaries. Therefore, the encoder-decoder was able to find a manifold parameterization that puts more emphasis on these regions which are usually compressed and difficult to regress over.

To conclude, this analysis showed how the encoder-decoder finds a balance in the optimized manifold parameterization to have all QoIs well-represented for regression. Having the QoIs smoothly distributed over the manifold, possibly in the logarithmic scale in case the complete range of QoI values are important, facilitated regression and hence provided a more accurate ROM. Future work is required to further investigate the working of the trainable scaling layer in other settings. Additionally, future work will focus on the implementation and validation of a ROM employing an optimized parameterization for practical 2D or 3D reacting flow configurations.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Grégoire Corlù: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data curation, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing, Visualization. **Kamila Zdybał**: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Resources, Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision. **Alessandro Parente**: Conceptualization, Methodology, Resources, Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Code availability

All code to obtain our results can be found in the following GitHub repository:

<https://github.com/GregoireCorluy/PV-optimization-for-ROM>

The code coming along with the preprint is archived on Zenodo:

<https://zenodo.org/records/18743453>

Data availability

All data required to reproduce the results of this study, including the datasets used for training the encoders–decoders as well as the trained models and saved outputs, are publicly available on Zenodo:

<https://zenodo.org/records/18743453>

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary material is submitted along with this manuscript.

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